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SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF THE GRAMMATICAL STRUCTURE OF A LANGUAGE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *English and Uzbek share similarities in their sentence structure, typically starting with the subject, followed by the verb, and then the object. Both languages modify verbs to indicate tense and the agent of the action. However, they diverge in several aspects. Uzbek nouns are categorized by type, influencing the appearance of other words in the sentence. Pronoun usage varies as well; English distinguishes between the subject and object pronouns, whereas Uzbek does not. These distinctions underscore the unique ways each language constructs sentences, reflecting their respective histories and cultures.*

Key words: *Grammatical structure, English, Uzbek, Case systems, Verb agreement, Word formation, Pronoun usage (фақат биринчи сўз катта харф билан ёзилади).*

Аннотация: *В английском и узбекском языках структура предложений схожа: обычно они начинаются с подлежащего, за которым следует глагол, а затем дополнение. В обоих языках глаголы модифицируются, чтобы указать время и средство действия. Однако они расходятся в нескольких аспектах. Узбекские существительные классифицируются по типам, влияющим на появление других слов в предложении. Кроме того, словообразование различается; В английском языке часто добавляются компоненты для создания новых слов, а в узбекском языке к существующим словам прикрепляются фрагменты. Использование местоимений также варьируется; В английском языке различаются местоимения субъекта и объекта, а в узбекском - нет. Эти различия подчеркивают уникальные способы построения предложений в каждом языке, отражающие их историю и культуру.*

Ключевые слова: *Грамматический строй, Английский язык, Узбекский язык, Падежные системы, Согласование глаголов, Словообразование, Употребление местоимений.*

Annotatsiya: Ingliz va o'zbek tillari jumla tuzilishida o'xshashliklarga ega bo'lib, odatda mavzudan boshlanadi, keyin esa fe'l, keyin esa ob'yekt keladi. Har ikki til ham fe'lni o'zgartirib, harakatning zamon va agentini bildiradi. Biroq, ular bir necha jihatdan farqlanadi. O'zbek tilidagi otlar gapdagi boshqa so'zlarning ko'rinishiga ta'sir ko'rsatib, turlarga bo'linadi. Bundan tashqari, so'z yasalishi farqlanadi; Ingliz tilida ko'pincha yangi so'z yaratish uchun komponentlar qo'shiladi, o'zbek tilida esa mavjud so'zlarga bo'laklar birlashtiriladi. Olmoshlardan foydalanish ham turlicha; Ingliz tili sub'ekt va ob'ekt olmoshlarini ajratadi, o'zbek tilida esa farq qilmaydi. Ushbu farqlar har bir tilning o'ziga xos tarixi va madaniyatini aks ettiruvchi jumlar tuzilishining o'ziga xos usullarini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz, O'zbek, til, o'xshashliklar, farqlar, olmoshlar, grammatik jins, jins kelishuvi, kasb unvonlari, egalik olmoshlari, madaniy ta'sir.

English and Uzbek have similar grammar rules like word order and verb changes, but they handle some things differently because of their unique histories.

English takes words from different languages, like Latin and French, so it can easily make new words by adding bits to them. For example, we can add "un-" to "happy" to make "unhappy." Also, English has separate pronouns for who's doing an action and who it's being done to, which helps make sentences clear.

Uzbek is more structured. It has specific types for nouns and changes words a lot to show their role in a sentence. For example, "doctor" looks different for a male doctor than for a female one. Uzbek also changes verbs a lot to show things like when an action happened or who's doing it.

By looking at these differences, we can see how language connects to culture and history. English and Uzbek grammar not only help people communicate but also reflect the traditions and identities of the people who speak them. Understanding these differences helps us learn more about each other and appreciate our cultural diversity.

English Sentence: «*You didn't tell us you weren't allowed to use magic outside school,*» **said Uncle Vernon.** "[Harry; 21]

Uzbek Sentence: "**Sen** xatingda yozibsan, Robiya! Bizni unashtirishdi, «ma'lum oshi bo'ldi», **debsan.**" [Ikki eshik orasi; 211]

1. Direct Speech: Both sentences feature direct speech, where the words spoken by a character are quoted within quotation marks ("...").

2. Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) Order: Both sentences generally follow the SVO word order. In English, "**Uncle Vernon**" (subject) **said** (verb) the quoted words. In Uzbek, "**Sen**" (subject) **debsan** (verb) the quoted words.

Differences:

1. Verb Forms: In English, the verb "said" is used to introduce the direct speech. In Uzbek, "debsan" serves the same function. However, the verb forms are different due to the conjugation rules of each language.

2. Word Order: While both sentences follow the SVO word order in the main clause, the structure of the quoted speech may vary. In English, the direct speech follows the pattern of subject-verb-object ("**you**"-"**didn't tell**"-"**us**"), whereas in Uzbek, it is more verb-subject-object ("**yozihsan**"-"**Sen**"-"**unashtirishdi**").

3. Pronoun Usage: In English, pronouns like "**you**" and "**us**" are explicitly used to indicate the speaker and the listener. In Uzbek, the pronouns are also explicit ("**Sen**" - "**you**", "**Bizni**" - "**us**"), but the order and case marking differ from English.

These differences and similarities illustrate how English and Uzbek languages structure sentences and convey information, reflecting their unique grammatical features and cultural contexts.

According to A. Gulomov, word formation is one of the effective ways to enrich the language lexicon. The basis of word formation is the vocabulary of the language, which includes all the root words as its core. In the literature, there are different views on word formation and word formation in word groups. Most of the literature emphasizes that word formation is characteristic of independent word groups. The phenomenon of word formation is mainly characteristic of independent categories. The composition of nouns, adjectives, verbs and adverbs is always enriched with new formations. In the literature, there are different views on word formation and word formation in word groups. Most of the literature emphasizes that word formation is characteristic of independent word groups. The phenomenon of word formation is mainly characteristic of independent categories.

[A. G'ulomov;34].

According to Ch. Fries (32) the morphological and the syntactic signals in the given sentence make us understand that "several actors acted upon some objects". This sentence which is a syntactic signal, makes the listener understand it as a declarative sentence whose grammatical meaning is actor - action - thing acted upon. One can easily change (transform) the sentence into the singular (A woggle ugged a diggle.), negative (A woggle did not ugg a diggle.), or interrogative (Did a woggle ugg a diggle?) All these operations are grammatical. Then what are the main units of grammar - structure. [Iriskulov;21].

Through comprehension and manipulation of these morphological and syntactic elements, individuals, whether learners or proficient users, possess the capacity to generate an extensive array of grammatically precise sentences. This proficiency is exemplified through transformative processes such as singularization, negation, and interrogation. Such components constitute the fundamental framework of linguistic structure, thereby facilitating effective communication and the conveyance of meaning.

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